

SUCCESSFUL INTEGRATION OF HUMAN ENGINEERING PRINCIPLES
IN SYSTEM DESIGN: A DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The need for human factors engineering in the acquisition process is receiving increased attention but is still misunderstood by some. This paper examines several facets of human factors engineering that deserve further discussion. The reasons for implementing a human factors program and utilizing human factors resources are identified. Five requirements necessary for the successful integration of an effective human factors program in today's complex weapons system acquisition environment are then identified and discussed. Finally, recommendations of what must be done to increase awareness and application of human factors in the procurement cycle are offered.

INTRODUCTION

The past has seen human factors (HF) considerations disregarded and even excluded from the design of new weapons systems. This paper presents working guidelines for the successful integration of human factors efforts into the system acquisition program. Areas that will be addressed include the personnel involved, the program manager's orientation towards human factors, the contractual requirements levied on the contractor, and the activities and interactions necessary to insure successful project completion. The discussions and recommendations presented here are intended to benefit government program management personnel through increased awareness of the HF field, but they are also relevant to HF engineers and contractors.

There are several compelling reasons why persons who direct the acquisition of modern weapons systems must be cognizant of the role of human factors in system development. The Government Accounting Office (GAO) released a report describing the increased need for HF, logistics support, and quality assurance in the systems acquisition process (1). Air Force Regulation (AFR) 800-15 directs and explains the use of HF in the acquisition process. The new speciality code identifier 2675A shred-out, for behavioral scientists specializing in HF, was recently created by the Air Force, reflecting

the need to identify personnel with human factors engineering experience.

The Air Force Systems Command (AFSC) has named HF as a special interest item for the Inspector General in 1987. General Bernard P. Randolph, AFSC Commander, in his Commander's Policies letter, has identified meeting the user's needs and requirements as one of the top priority goals for the Command. This increased emphasis on HF by the GAO, the Department of Defense, and Air Force leadership clearly demonstrates that top-level management is committed to effective implementation of human factors considerations into the procurement process.

Increased cognitive and workload demands placed upon the weapon system operator and maintainer due to the system's increased capabilities in information display and control present persistent and difficult challenges (2). The solutions to these challenges can only be found with the application of human factors principles during system design. The GAO report cited above named three facts supporting the inclusion of HF in system design:

1. Human errors account for at least 50% of the failures of major weapons systems.
2. Neglect of human factors in early planning has caused serious and costly problems.
3. There has been considerable effort to adapt man to the constraints built into hardware instead of using human factors design criteria to initially design a system compatible with the human's limitations.

There are several aspects of the current system design process that result in the problems noted above. First among these is the implementation of immature technology simply because it can be done without regard for how the technology enhances (or degrades) the system. Air Force Manual 1-1, Basic Aerospace Doctrine of the USAF, describes this problem of balancing the rewards of tomorrow's technology versus today's need for realistic war-fighting capability (3). Human factors engineers can provide the program manager with information vital to determining the trade-offs between these two concerns.

Overreliance on the human operator's ability to adapt and inattention to the intended user's desires and requirements are also significant sources of problems. Ignorance of the intended user population's skill levels and attributes, as well as postponement or complete disregard for HF considerations to the detriment of the system, are also causes of the problems revealed by the GAO study. A competent human factors engineer can provide the information necessary to remedy these problems.

With these aspects in mind, it becomes obvious that human factors programs must be implemented in today's technologically advanced weapons system procurement arena. Effective use of HF during the design and test stages of the procurement will result in long-term savings of time, money, and lives, as well as increased operational performance and user satisfaction.

Indeed, the emphasis placed upon HF will differ with each program. It is the responsibility of the human factors engineer (HFE) to provide program management with the information necessary to determine the needs of the particular program. Armed with this information, the program manager can successfully employ his HF resources for the benefit of both the system and the Air Force.

DISCUSSION

A strong and effective human factors program includes these assets:

1. Government Expertise. The government human factors expert must be trained and experienced in both HF principles and the DOD procurement process.
2. Contractor Expertise. The contractor must provide a knowledgeable and experienced team of HF professionals who are acquainted with the government acquisition process.
3. Program Management Support. The government and contractor program managers must both realize the need and importance of human factors in the development of a successful system and have confidence in and provide the necessary support to their HF experts.
4. Complete Contractual Documentation. A thorough and well-written system specification stating the requirements of the program and a Statement of Work (SOW) that clearly addresses the HF program and includes appropriate human factors Contract Data Requirements List (CDRL) items.
5. Government-Contractor Communication. Frequent exchange of information and ideas must occur between all cognizant personnel to monitor program progress and respond to development questions.

The government HF expert needs to be brought on board as soon as the program manager begins developing the Request for Proposal (RFP) for a new system. The program manager must include an HF expert early to ensure that HF concerns are adequately addressed in the RFP. Contact can be made with the user in order to determine his needs and allow the HF engineer to fully understand the task and mission requirements of the system. This understanding can be developed through on-site visits to the users under the auspices of the Air Force's Blue Two program or through similar operational visiting programs. The Blue Two program allows USAF and contractor personnel to travel to the end-user's facilities and get first-hand information of how the item will be used and maintained. At this time, the HF expert will be able to determine what the HF requirements will be and advise the program manager of the amount of HF support necessary for the program.

The HF expert will then be able to task the contractor through the SOW with appropriate CDRL items to ensure that the user's requirements are met. A well-written RFP and SOW with appropriate CDRL items will result in better proposals from the contractors and allow the strengths and weaknesses of each human factors program to be identified. Documented government requirements for CDRLs and specific project milestone completion dates allow the contractor human factors specialist to do his job better since he can now approach his program manager with options to meet the documented requirements. A contractor that has an experienced human factors engineering staff and is familiar with the federal acquisition process will tend to reduce the risk associated with the program.

The HF expert who developed the RFP and source selection criteria should be used in evaluating the contractors' proposals in order to reduce the risk of accepting a proposal that does not meet the system's requirements. The HF evaluator must provide sufficient rationale to explain each offeror's human factors program, in terms of meeting the source selection criteria, and the potential risks associated with each.

Desirable proposals will clearly outline a human factors program with scheduled milestones including (but not limited to) design reviews, technical interchange meetings, Blue Two visits, user's group conferences, and system tests. The schedule should also identify any human factors tasks being performed before the first major design review. The proposal should also describe the relationships between the HF group and other engineering disciplines to insure incorporation of HF concerns throughout the design process. Up-front analysis and inclusion of human factors concerns into the system design reduce risk and allow for timely completion of the system development phase.

Upon contract award, the government and contractor HF experts must meet to discuss the philosophy of the program and begin planning for the most immediate concerns of the program. It is important at this time to build a good working relationship to facilitate the flow of information between both parties. A regular dialogue must be maintained between the government and contractor to insure that problems are rapidly addressed and solved. This also allows the government HF expert to know the status of the system's development while allowing the contractor a ready source of information about the user's needs and the system's requirements. Regular communication between government and contractor HF experts will lead to a more effective HF program and consequently, a better operational system

RECOMMENDATIONS

To realize the benefits gained by implementation of an effective human factors program, there are several actions the procuring agency must pursue:

1. The procuring agency must hire sufficient numbers of well trained human factors engineers and provide opportunities for them to maintain currency in their field and pursue higher education.

2. The procuring agency must provide training and opportunities for human factors experts to become well-versed in the federal acquisition process, techniques of writing the system specification, SOW, RFP, and source selection evaluation.

3. Program managers must be made aware of the need for human factors expertise in the development of all weapons systems and must make use of the human factors expertise available to them. AFSC Regulation 550-10 directs program managers to ponder "each decision in light of the user's needs (4)." Consulting their human factors resources will give the program managers insight into the user's perspective.

4. The government must insure that the contractor realizes the need for trained human factors expertise on the engineering team.

Although the government does hire trained personnel to become HF experts and provides training opportunities, there is room for improvement. Current manning appears to be adequate for today's demand, but, as increasing emphasis is placed upon human factors, more and better trained personnel will be needed. More time and money must be available to pursue additional education to allow the HF engineers to maintain their skills and keep abreast of the latest techniques. Several training courses are offered to instruct new hires about the systems acquisition cycle, but although every effort is made to send everyone, the quality of each course differs, and work commitments sometime preclude attendance.

It is important to overcome the stereotypical view (held by both managers and engineers alike) that human factors is just "common sense" or gold-plating. Human factors engineers do make meaningful and vital contributions to every program's success. We cannot afford to ignore the evidence any longer. As the impact of command initiatives is felt and as the level of technology continues to rise, more DOD personnel must come to realize the importance of adequately addressing human factors issues in system development or the loss of life, equipment, and operational capability will continue. In today's battlefield of compressed time and space, we must possess the most capability we can get for our procurement dollars.

REFERENCES

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